

Annika Rockenberger

Literary Evaluation Between Ethics and Aesthetics

1. Scandal Books and Literary Controversies

Not all books but *some* have, at least for some time, the disposition to provoke many readers, to induce scandals and controversies. These books arouse public commotion and indignation, attract and pool the attention of the media: for themselves as well as for the people involved: the authors, publishers, and critics. *Actual* scandals, debates, and controversies about works of literature most often relate to either substantial agreement or widespread disagreement concerning *axiological moral values*, and thus, the *standards for ethically judging* literary works and authors.

In this regard, controversies might enforce an *explicit elaboration* of ethical arguments, or more precisely, the disclosure and justification of empirical and normative *premises* of ethical value judgments. And what's more, such phenomena may shed some light on the individual and social *functions* attributed to literature, and may also reveal shared beliefs regarding the 'nature of literature' and the according conventions of literary practice, that is: the rules for treating literature *as literature*.

The routine of *ordinary* reviews might display such *explicit* reflections to a much lesser extent than the *programmatic* contributions to literary debates in prestigious national newspapers and magazines. Usually, subsequent reviews – for example in online media – ensue from the agenda setting of initial programmatic reviews that often are quoted within the work's paratext, namely in peritextual blurbs and other epitextual messages already *suggesting* the controversial status of the work.

2. Ethical Criticism: For and Against

However, 'controversial' books seem to be suited perfectly for a certain way of approaching literature usually labeled as 'ethical criticism' or 'moralism'. Among the prominent advocates are Wayne C. Booth, Martha C. Nussbaum or Noël Carroll. (A bit simplified) these authors take the view that, to be an *adequate* representation of literary

works, critical reception must also recognize ethically relevant properties of the work, and that aesthetical and ethical appraisal of art are eventually inseparable.

Accordingly, literary works may have a practical user value inasmuch as they could function as “moral lessons” or “moral laboratories”, could offer ethical advice, present ethical role models, or illustrate or visualize abstract ethical views and conflicts. Thus, reading literature could nurture cognitive and emotional ethical competences, provoke empathy and compassion with fictitious characters, introduce innovative moral perspectives, stabilize, irritate or subvert deep-rooted ethical intuitions, or simply ‘provoke ethical reflection’. A more defensive, weaker version of this position holds that ethical criticism poses – at least in specific cases – *one* legitimate approach to literature among many others.

Expressively *rejecting* an instrumentalist ‘exploitation of art’, *autonomy aesthetics* on the other hand publicizes ‘uninterested appreciation’ as a defense response to the heteronomy, massification and commercialization of literature and as a refusal of its reduction to mere purposive rationality and instrumental usefulness. High-minded *aesthetic* experience and delightful delectation are considered as delivering the individual from social restraints.

According to this normative position, literature owes its functional significance primarily to its suitability for an *aesthetical* use: the sole objective of a work of literature is to be beautiful, well structured and well written. Obviously, this *positive* functional statement also implies a *negative* one, namely the idea that literature is without any moral, social, cognitive, or extra-literary purposes.

Like ‘moralism’ aesthetical ‘autonomism’ comes in strong and weak, absolute and moderate versions. Still, influential proponents of this school of thought, like Richard A. Posner, hold that [quote] “the proper criteria for evaluating art are aesthetic rather than ethical.” [end of quote] A *conceptual* version of this argument points out that ‘interested’ approaches, applying ethical evaluations or political utilizations, actually contradict the common understanding of the very notions of ‘art’ and ‘literature’, and thus violate basic intuitions, expectations and conventions ruling ‘proper’ ways of reception.

It is difficult to prove, however, that these highly abstract and sophisticated theoretical debates concerning the legitimacy of ethical criticism of literature have or had any

(direct) influence on *practical* criticism. According to Noël Carroll there has been [quote] “a gap between theory and practice with respect to the ethical criticism of arts throughout the twentieth century” [end of quote]. Still, there might be similar patterns of argumentation and shared normative premises concerning ethical theory as well as aesthetics and literary theory.

In this talk I won't take part in *normative* philological or philosophical debates regarding the question of how we *should* evaluate literature, and if only those practices of criticism can be *adequate* which additionally, primarily or exclusively expose the (negative or positive) *ethical* values of a given literary work.

Are there compelling reasons to accept one of these normative positions – apart from personal preferences merely *passed off* as supra-individual obligations? And do we really have to *choose*? Is this really a go/no-go type of decision? Aren't there *many* different ways of approaching literary works, depending mainly on our own interests? As a *pluralist* I tend to answer in the affirmative. But, because of time constraints I cannot dig any deeper into this rather theoretical debate.

3. Ethical Criticism in a Descriptive Perspective

Instead, I am proposing an *expressively* descriptive and empirical approach: However, my question will *not* be, whether or not we *should* engage in ethical criticism. I am rather presuming that we – at least some of us, at least some of the time – *already do*. There has been very little research dealing with the question of how – or if at all – professional and lay readers *actually* respond to ethically relevant features of either an author's communicative intentions and actions, to moral implications of modes of narration, story worlds and fictitious characters, or to the ramifications, whether intended or not, of reading a literary work.

How do *actual* readers incorporate ethical arguments into their positive or negative value judgments concerning literary works and authors? What's the very *object* of these judgments? Which *features* of a given object of evaluation are exposed as ethically relevant? What are the general ethical frameworks and the specific axiological or the attributed manifest values that readers refer to? Are those references explicit or implicit? How are we to reconstruct implicit, remote evaluations? Do readers usually give reasons for their ethical value judgments? Is there any *argumentative* justification?

Are there argumentative patterns? Are ethical and aesthetic evaluations somehow related? And if so, how? What's the relationship between *normative* aesthetics and *practical* value judgments? Do readers somehow draw on the debate between aesthetical 'autonomism' and 'moralism'? Is there consensus or dissent among critics? Which functions, purposes, and effects are ascribed to literature in general and literary genres and individual works in particular?

Empirical questions like these are hardly ever addressed, let alone answered. And for the matter of moral values, functions, and effects *actually* attributed to literary works in *ordinary* practices of reception, there is very little we know.

Concerning this rather unsatisfactory situation, my constructive proposal is to approach the issue by investigating the critical reception of *one* contemporary work of literature.

But keep in mind that this is only a *workshop report*. So far I can only provide the outlines my case study and give some tentative remarks on the probable outcomes.

I investigate German reviews of the hotly debated young-adult novel *Intet* by Danish writer Janne Teller, originally published in 2000, and translated into German in 2010. Undoubtedly, the novel can be said to be a 'controversial' book. If the headlines are to be believed, the book is very likely to be criticized as ethically irresponsible, immoral, critical of religion, depressing, disgusting, cruel, potentially traumatizing, misanthropic and nihilistic. *Intet* was even considered to pose a risk to young adults and was temporarily banned from Danish and Norwegian schools. That is: the book was deemed responsible even for *unintended*, yet predictable, effects on the future beliefs, emotions, and actions of young readers prone to unsound 'ethical confusion'.

Drawing on my own reading experience and significant hints in the work's paratext, it seems initially plausible to assume, that not only aesthetic but also *ethical* values may play a part in the work's critical evaluation. I am well aware of the fact that this heuristics is biased. A *representative* sample allowing more general conclusions concerning the moral evaluation of literature should have been randomly selected. Still, focusing on the 'how' rather than the 'if' may at least grant a limited insight into the *practices* of ethical criticism.

It is my objective to show how Teller's novel *actually* is evaluated *in the light of ethics*. That is: I am asking for the relevance of ethical arguments in concrete cases of literary evaluation. However, I will *not* evaluate these critical reviews in terms of argumentative

consistence, balance, fairness or factual correctness. Instead I confine myself to descriptive analyses and explanations.

Given the possible tendency of critical reviews to diverge from the concrete object in favor of detached expressions of moral opinions, I am not interested in *general* ethical statements and arguments, but only in those which assertorically *refer* to the literary work or certain properties of it; *qualify* these properties as being in accordance or at variance with relevant moral or ethical standards; and *display* a non-epistemic, usually affirmative attitude towards these standards.

The reconstruction of *ethical* value judgments requires their identification and their differentiation from other types of evaluation. Thus, we need a heuristic explication of terms like ‘moral’ or ‘ethical’. In my understanding these terms are used to qualify persons, actions, beliefs, and attitudes as complying with those norms, standards, or principles of human coexistence and interpersonal interaction to which *general validity is ascribed*. I admit that it is difficult to clearly differentiate between moral norms and mere mores – say, customs or principles of decency. As for the reconstruction of ethical value judgments, it seems to be beneficial to ensue, at least heuristically, from a *broad* understanding of the terms ‘ethical’ and ‘moral’.

Strictly speaking, artificial *objects* like works of literature – other than authors and fictitious characters, their assertions and actions respectively – can *not* be subject of ethical evaluation. So it poses an interesting question to whom or what ethical *responsibility* is being attributed in critical reviews. This poses a problem especially for those immanent features of the work (or ideas derived from the work’s content), which may be interpreted as implicit ‘moral messages’ or ‘moral implications’, but cannot be attributed to one of the communicative instances – author, narrator, character – immediately.

In my analyses, however, there are two main questions to be answered:

- (1) What are the *empirical* features of Teller’s novel that are qualified as relevant for negative or positive ethical value judgments?
- (2) What are the *normative* ethical theories and axiological standards according to which these features are qualified as ethically relevant and are evaluated ethically?

Additionally (3), I try to reconstruct implicit or explicit normative assumptions regarding the ‘nature of literature’, the *functions* and *effects* of literature, and the

appropriate approach to literary works. I already indicated that aesthetical theories might function as a secondary normative framework for the ascription of non-aesthetic values, as well as for the *balancing* of non-aesthetic and aesthetic values.

The corpus I examine is selection of *verbal* acts of evaluation, namely ca. 200 critical reviews of *Intet*. I am *not* implying that either this pragmatic selection of reviews or my results are in any way *representative* for the contemporary literary criticism in general. However, I won't constrain myself to professionals' critiques in well-known (printed) newspapers, feuilletons and magazines, but also consider the non-professional, lay critics' reviews to be found on the World Wide Web (mainly on *Amazon* but also on private blogs or video reviews on *YouTube*) and point out the existing differences and similarities in their critical practices.

I am well aware that 'expert' reviews by (prestigious) professional literary critics pose important focal points of a literary work's public reception; quotations from print reviews might even become a part of the book's peritext or the publisher's epitext. Still, restricting oneself to the 'elite' of professional reviewers *only* does imply a rather *limited*, unrepresentative view of the pervasive social phenomenon of literary criticism and its changing faces. The same holds true for the common restriction to so-called 'high' or 'real literature'. Regarding the *objects* of investigation professional (institutional) literary studies are characterized not only by a *generic* devaluation of certain types of literature but also by a *social* exclusion of certain groups of recipients. So far, there is very little (empirical) research regarding literary criticism *on the Internet* in general and online *lay* criticism in particular. The same holds true for the common devaluation of so-called 'functional literature'.

4. Ethical Value Judgments in Critical Reviews of *Nothing*

Janne Teller's *Intet* is a sophisticated young-adult novel. Here's a short summary: On the first day of seventh grade, one of the pupils, Pierre Anthon, announces that "nothing matters" and so "nothing is worth doing". He walks out of the classroom, ascends the pulpit of a plum tree and keeps spreading his nihilistic message for months to come. His classmates however scramble to prove him wrong. They begin to assemble a "heap of meaning" in an abandoned sawmill. Each child must add a cherished possession of the others' choosing. The need of the children to avenge their losses gains momentum and

spins out of control. The more painful the loss is, the more meaning it has, or so the juveniles conclude. A pious Muslim boy is forced to give up his prayer rug; a pious Christian boy has to steal a crucifix from the village church. One girl has to hand over her pet hamster, another girl has to excavate the coffin of her late younger brother, and yet another girl must contribute the head of a beloved dog. A boy demands a girl's innocence. That girl demands the forefinger of the guitar playing class idol. By now, the "heap of meaning" has turned into a pile of smelly debris. Still, Pierre Anthon keeps mocking his peers. Even after the "heap of meaning" has been discovered by the police and the parents, declared to be art and sold to an American museum, he just says that *selling* those 'meaningful' things actually has proven his point. Eventually the children batter the disturber to death and burn the sawmill to the ground.

Even a cursory inspection of the critical reviews shows that about 60 percent of the texts include moral evaluations in the broadest sense, albeit mostly indirectly or implicitly. Provided it was possible to *clearly* identify ethical value judgments, most of them appeared to be positive and argumentatively harmonized with positive *aesthetic* evaluations in favor of a positive *overall* evaluation of the work.

As for the *objects* of evaluation: Firstly, the nihilistic *theme* of the novel is subject to ethical judgments. Secondly, the actions, beliefs and attitudes of fictitious *characters* (as *internal* features of the story) are ethically judged. Thirdly, the *mode of narrative* presentation is either criticized or praised, or more precisely: the author's descriptive approach, the neutral *tone* and the lack of moral distancing. Fourthly, the potential *effects* on young – and allegedly impressionable – readers of the novel are used as empirical premises of value judgments. Fifthly, the author herself is being held responsible – for better or for worse – for the overall 'message' of her work and the (alleged) effects it has on readers.

Of course, this is a rather heuristic differentiation because in critical reviews these aspects are usually combined argumentatively. For example, the positive effect of the novel to be thought provoking is *ascribed* to the neutral mode of presentation.

As for the *normative assumptions* regarding the 'nature of literature' and rules of literary production and reception, it is an interesting finding, that the neutral mode of narration, the 'moral subtlety' so to speak, is being exposed as a positive *aesthetic* quality of the novel: Teller does not lecture or indoctrinate her readers; which is obviously compatible with 'autonomistic' conventions. On the contrary, the very same

aspect of the work is considered to be a *moral* flaw: Teller does not use the mode of narration or the composition of the story to distance herself from the ‘immoral’ content of her novel. There seems to be a conflict of norms here. One way to re-harmonize strong moral evaluations with the defaults of ‘autonomism’ is the indication of a specific *generic* realm in which certain literary conventions are suspended or weakened. Obviously, young-adult literature is considered to be such an ethically sensitive realm – especially regarding cognitive or affective effects on the young readers’ minds. Then again, there are meta-commentaries on *Amazon* (and in readers’ forums) re-invoking established norms of literary reception by arguing that even young-adult literature is *actually* literature and must therefore be read *as literature*. Of course, such statements contribute to the argumentative complexity of ethical value judgments. – But time’s up, and I cannot pursue this any further.

Let me conclude: Analyzing critical reviews, detecting and reconstructing complex ethical evaluations is a rather difficult task, and so far I only scratched the surface a bit. But in my view this effort is unavoidable if we want to bring down ‘ethical criticism’ from the abstract spheres of philosophical reflection and the level of mere assertions to the level of concrete empirical research and thus the level of valid insights.

Thank you for your attention!